

Impact of Working Capital Management on the Profitability of the Cement Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract

Working Capital Management is the golden brick in the world of finance. It helps in making the management decisions of the firms. When the Working Capital is managed improperly that is when too large or too small amount of Working Capital is used, results in negative impact on the firms. Therefore a balance level of Working Capital is required to have greater profits. In our research we examined the impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability. We used a sample of two cement companies listed in Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) for the time period of (2001-2011) and the number of observation are ten. The reason for doing a research is to develop a significant statistical relation between profitability, Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and the components (Number of Days Inventory, Number of Days Account Receivables and Number of Days Payables). Our research analysis concluded that there is significant inverse relation between Profitability calculated through Returns on Assets and CCC. Managers can make profits for the firms by maintaining CCC properly and controlling the number of days account receivables and number of days inventory.

Keywords: Working Capital Management; Profitability: Evidence From Cement Sector of Pakistan.

Introduction

Working Capital Management (WCM) is vital for the growth of the organization. Many studies have been done to check the relationship between WCM and profitability of the firms. In the year 1980 Smith concluded a significant impact of WCM on Profitability and Risk factors of the firms, and concluded increase in their overall value.

Efficient management of the Working Capital is the basis of prosperous business and duty of every manager to keep it running, generate profit by using the Cash Flows. Working Capital is as important as our red blood cells. Firms of any nature profit oriented, people oriented need sufficient Working Capital. It is important for balancing levels of liquidity, Solvency, Survival and firms Profitability.

From the study done in 2004, Eljelly while making the comparison of the Liquidity and Profitability among the firms concluded that management of the Working Capital should be done properly. In a similar study Harris (2005) studied that WCM ensures the capability of the firms to finance Short term assets and Liabilities.

Working Capital is said to be the Current Assets of the firm where the current assets are Cash, Cash Equivalents, Account Receivables and inventories. According to Ricci & Di Vito in the year 2004, proper usage of the Working Capital ensures equilibrium between Profitability and Risk. This job can be done by continuous supervision of Working Capital and its components that are Account Receivables, Inventories

and Account Payables. In the year 2005 Filbeck and Krueger said that profitability of the business depends on skills, knowledge and experience of the financial manager.

In the theory of Risk and Return high Risk investments will tend to give higher Returns. Therefore firm with higher liquidity of the Working Capital may have lower Risk than lower profits. While on the other side firms have lower liquidity of Working Capital faces higher Risk and results high profits. In the management of the Working Capital firms should consider all the elements of both account and should try to keep equilibrium between Risk and Return. Proper management of Working Capital is being expected to have a positive impact in making firms value.

In corporate finance researchers focused a lot on Long term financial decisions especially in Capital Structure, Dividends, Investments or firm Valuation decision. There are to crucial elements of the total assets that are Short term assets and Liabilities which should be studied with concentration. The current research will help to understand the factors which shape up the requirements of the Working Capital in Pakistan. In the corporate world WCM is the tool of developing the shareholder value. According to Howorth and Westhead 2003 firms effort to control a balance level of Working Capital to have a maximum value of the firm.

In the year 2010, Dong and Su said that efficient management of the Working Capital has a vital role in the corporate world in order to increase the worth of the shareholders. In the year 2011, Al Shubiri said proper

management of the Working Capital provides the competitive advantage to the firms on their competitors and enables them to deal immediately with the abnormal changes in the business environment.

Lastly in the field of managerial firms WCM has a vital role with both positive and negative impacts on the business as it has significant effect on the Profitability of the firms. The current research is being done to have better understanding between WCM and Profitability. The mission of the WCM is to make balance in every component of Working Capital.

According to Fildeck and Kruegar (2005), Profitability of firms is associated with capabilities of the manager; if the managers are capable he can properly manage Inventory, Receivables and payables. Firms will have availability of finance for the expansion projects if it reduce its financing cost and minimize the amount of investment which is being blocked in current assets. In the study of non-optimal levels of current assets and liabilities and rising up to the balance level managers should contribute a lot of their time and efforts. (Lamberson 1995) a balance level of Working Capital is the one in which equilibrium is achieved between efficiency and risk. It requires a continuous monitoring the balance level of the Working Capital.

Objectives of study

Management of Working Capital is important for every firm. It is necessary to know how it affects the profitability of a firm? We will find the impact of the working capital management on the profitability of the firm by exploring the ways of better usage of working capital.

Literature Review

According to corporate WCM is a vital issue that's why researchers from dissimilar areas study it with different angles and in different fields.

According to Deloof M. 2003 majority of firms had a huge sum of money invested in Working Capital. Therefore we can say that the manner by which Working Capital is managed has a major effect on Profitability of those firms. He used Correlation and Regression test and accomplished a huge negative association between gross operating income and the number of day's inventories, account receivables and account payables of Belgian firms. On the proof of these outcomes he recommended that dropping the number of days account receivables and inventories to the logical minimum level the managers could generate value for their shareholders. The negative link between account payables and

Profitability is consistent with the outlook that lower profitable firms stay longer to pay their bills.

Lazaridis and Tryfonidis in 2006 saw an inverse correlation between profitability and the CCC which was being taken as the evaluation WCM efficiency. It seems that operational profitability shows how managers will take action in provision of organizing the Working Capital of the firms. The facts gathered were from the firms listed in Athens stock exchange (ASE) via a sample of almost three hundred firms and later on the number fall down to one thirty one for a period of 2001 to 2004 through regression analysis and descriptive statistics. By management of the CCC and holding every different section (Account Receivables, Account Payables, and Inventory) to a best favorable level managers could generate high earnings for their firms. Shah and Sana (2006) accomplished that there is a strong negative correlation between gross profit and Working Capital ratios excluding average payment period which is positively correlated to gross profit by examining oil and gas sector of Pakistan.

Rahman A and Nasr M (2007) calculated that the majority of the firms in Pakistan have huge sum of money invested in the Working Capital. So it is predictable that the major impact on the profitability of those firms is through the manner by which Working Capital is managed. Through panel data regression study of cross sectional and time sequence of data for a sample of the Pakistani firms which are listed on Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE). They have concluded that there is a huge negative association between net operating Profitability and standard collection period, Inventory turnover in days, Average payment periods and CCC. According to outcomes by dropping the number of days, account receivables and inventories to the logical minimum managers can generate worth for the shareholders. The less profitable firms will stay longer to give their bills because there is strong negative relationship between profitability and account payables. WCM always play a vital role in small and medium size companies. For external financing these companies use their assets as current assets and also as current liabilities. The purpose to do research was to present an empirical proof regarding the effect of WCM on the Profitability through descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and mean values via return on assets quartiles and effect of WCM on return on assets of a sample of eight thousand eight hundred seventy two from the time period between 1996 and 2002 (Teruel and Solano. 2007).

Afza and Nazir (2008) conducted a research in association between aggressive Working Capital policies for seventeen industries and public Ltd firms listed on (KSE) for the time period of 1998 and 2003. The study

gives them the major difference between Working Capital investment and financing policies in different industries.

Singh and Pandey (2008) had put an effort to conduct research on working capital variables and the effect of WCM on the Profitability of Hindalco industries Ltd between the time period of 1990 and 2007. The outcome of their research showed them that Current ratio, Receivable turnover Ratio (RTO) and Working Capital to total assets ratio had a major impact on the profitability of the Hindalco industries Ltd.

Azhar and Noriza (2010) had chosen one hundred and seventy two Malaysian companies to calculate the

impact of WCM on the Profitability of the firms. Huge negative correlation in Working Capital Variables and companies performance came after their study.

Hill, Kelly and High field (2010), conducted a research on the variables of Working Capital. They studied the records of three thousand three hundred and forty three firms between time frame of 1996 and 2006. After the research they come to know that there is negative correlation between Working Capital requirement and increase in sales and there is positive relation with operating Cash flows and access to the capital markets.

Proposed Model

Figure 1.0

Explanation of Model

In our study we have taken the vital variable that affect WCM of the cement firms in Pakistan. Selection of the variables is influenced by the past studies in WCM. Variables used being to examine the hypothesis of our thesis is give below.

The dependent variable we used in our research is Return on Assets (ROA). We calculated this variable by dividing Earnings before Interest and Taxes (EBIT) by assets. We used number of day's receivables for the collection policy. It is calculated as a ratio of accounts receivable to sales and multiplying the answer by 365. We used number of days account payable for the payment policy and it is calculated as the ratio of account payable to purchases and multiplying the answer by 365. We used days inventory for the inventory policy it is calculated as the ratio of inventory to Cost of goods sold (CGS) and multiplying the answer by 365. We used CCC as a primary factor of WCM. CCC is the independent variable of our thesis which is calculated by subtracting the sum of number of days account receivable and number of day's inventory from number of days account receivable.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant effect of CCC on the profitability of Cement sector.

H1: There is significant effect of CCC on the profitability of Cement sector.

There is a significant negative impact of CCC on the profitability of the cement sector of Pakistan. CCC includes number of day's account receivables, number of day's inventory and number of day's payables. Whenever the CCC goes high the value of the profitability of the firm will go down.

Methodology

Population of our research is the two cement companies that are listed on (KSE). There are twenty eight companies respectively in the cement sector of Pakistan. We took two large and famous cement firms that are Best Way Cements, and Cherat Cements listed on (KSE).

The data has been gathered from the website of (KSE), which includes balance sheets and income statements regarding the above mention public limited companies for the time period of (2001 to 2011). These companies give the overall review of the cement sector of Pakistan. We used the regression and correlation analysis to find out the results.

Data Analysis

We have conducted two studies that are study 1 and study 2, we examined the gathered data by using Pearson correlation (2-tailed), Model summary and ANOVA. First table tells us about the Pearson correlation (2-tailed) for the independent variable CCC and dependent Variable Returns on Assets (ROA) while other tables Model summary and ANOVA are being used to find a regression of variables taken for the research.

Regression and Analysis study 1 (Best Way Cement)

Table 1.1 Correlation

		ROA	CCC
ROA	Pearson Correlation	1	-.586*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.047
	N	10	10
CCC	Pearson Correlation	-.586*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.047	
	N	10	10

The above table tells us Pearson correlation results between the independent Variable Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and dependent Variable Return on Assets (ROA). The outcome of correlation test gave an inverse coefficient – 0.586, with p-value of (0.047) where N are the number of observations. The outcome gives a significant and inverse correlation among the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and Return on Assets (ROA). It shows that the outcome is highly significant at $\alpha = 5\%$, and that if the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC increases one time it will have a negative effect of – 0.586 on the profitability and it will result in a decrease in profitability.

According to our research we come to know that if the firm is able to reduce CCC time intervals, then the firms will work efficiently to manage the working capital. This efficiency will help the firm to get higher returns.

Table 1.2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.776 ^a	.601	.561	.162

The above table tells us about the Model Summary. The adjusted R square is the percent of the variance in the dependent variable examined by the independent variables and is 56.1% where R square is 60.1% and R is 77.6%. R change is 16.2%.

Table 1.3 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1840.255	4	.004	.775	.003 ^a
	Residual	10386.000	357	.001		
	Total	12236.255	354			

Here is the table of ANOVA analysis, which shows that the model is highly significant at 0.003 and it is also proved that F-statistics is 0.775 which indicates a significant relationship among the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and Return on Assets (ROA)

Table 1.4 Coefficients

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	31.961	11.172		2.861	.016	-.031	.196
CCC	-2.741	.708	-.297	3.874	.003	-.004	.002

Regression tells us about the strength of relation between dependent variable and independent variable. In the model summary, R tells about the correlation between the dependent variable and independent variable. R-square tells about the variance in the dependent variable Returns on Assets (ROA) because of independent variable Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC). Beta (B) shows the change in the dependent variable because of independent variable. These are un-standardized coefficients because they are measured in their natural units.

The equation for regression is $y = \alpha + \beta X$. Where y represents the dependent variable (Returns on Assets), α is the constant, b is the change in independent variable because of dependent variable, and x is the independent variable (Cash Conversion Cycle). The regression equation for this study is

$$\text{Returns on Assets} = 31.961 + (-2.741) (\text{Cash Conversion Cycle})$$

31.961 is the constant and -2.741 is the value of which shows the change in dependent variable because of independent variable. So therefore if the Cash Conversion Cycle increases one time it will have a negative impact of - 2.741 on the profitability and it will result in a decrease in profitability.

Regression and Analysis study 2 (Cherat Cement)

Table 2.1 Correlation

		ROA	CCC
ROA	Pearson Correlation	1	-.762*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.028
	N	10	10
CCC	Pearson Correlation	-.762*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	
	N	10	10

The above table tells us Pearson correlation results between the independent Variable Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and dependent Variable Return on Assets (ROA). The outcome of correlation test gave an inverse coefficient - 0.762, with p-value of (0.028) where N are the number of observations. The outcome gives a significant and inverse correlation among the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and Return on Assets (ROA). It shows that the outcome is highly significant at $\alpha = 5\%$, and that if the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC increases one time it will have a negative effect of - 0.762 on the profitability and it will result in a decrease in profitability.

According to our research we come to know that if the firm is able to reduce CCC time intervals, then the firms will work efficiently to manage the working capital. This efficiency will help the firm to get higher returns.

Table 2.2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.861 ^a	.738	.726	.178

The above table tells us about the Model Summary. The adjusted R square is the percent of the variance in the dependent variable examined by the independent variables and is 72.6% where R square is 73.8% and R is 86.1%. R change is 17.8%.

Table 2.3 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.241	3	3.311	53.017	.000 ^a
	Residual	4.682	76	0.063		
	Total	17.927	78			

Here is the table of ANOVA analysis, which shows that the model is highly significant at 0.000 and it is also proved that F-statistics is 53.017 which indicate a significant relationship among the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC and Return on Assets (ROA).

Table 2.4 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	0.092	.163		-.563	.573	-.031	.143
	CCC	-2.346	.293	-.571	-7.978	.000	.003	.004

Regression tells us about the strength of relation between dependent variable and independent variable. In the model summary, R tells about the correlation between the dependent variable and independent variable. R-square tells about the variance in the dependent variable Returns on Assets (ROA) because of independent variable Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC). Beta (B) shows the change in the dependent variable because of independent variable. These are un-standardized coefficients because they are measured in their natural units.

The equation for regression is $y = \alpha + \beta X$. Where y represents the dependent variable (Returns on Assets), α is the constant, b is the change in independent variable because of dependent variable, and x is the independent variable (Cash Conversion Cycle). The regression equation for this study was

$$\text{Returns on Assets} = 0.092 + (-2.346) (\text{Cash Conversion Cycle})$$

0.092 is the constant and -2.346 is the value of B that is the un-standardized coefficient which shows the change in dependent variable because of independent variable. So therefore if the Cash Conversion Cycle increases one time it will have a negative impact of - 2.346 on the

profitability and it will result in a decrease in profitability.

Conclusion

Working capital management is vital in making firms management decisions. When management of the Working Capital is not done properly that is too large and too small allocation of the Working Capital will make the firm non efficient and the profits of the short term investments will decrease. When the firm has less amount of Working Capital it misses many business opportunities and therefore firms faces liquidity crisis. The current research tells that there is a significant negative relation between Profitability and CCC that we used as a measure of Working Capital Management. Hence it can be said that Profitability teaches managers

how to act in managing the Working Capital. In our research we have examined decrease in profitability is because of increase in the CCC. Therefore WCM has a significant negative impact on the Profitability of the firms.

Researches on Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability in different sectors of Pakistan are not so much common. Researches should do study for it in order to maximize the profitability of the firms.

We have studied the impact of Cash Conversion Cycle on the Profitability of the cement Sector of Pakistan. In future the researchers can find the relationship of every single component of the Cash Conversion Cycle that is Inventory Period, Receivable Period and Payment Period with profitability. Researchers can also find the impact of Working Capital Management on profitability in other sector like textile, fertilizers, chemicals etc.

Recommendations

The inverse relation between Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and firm's Profitability recommends that low profitable firms will try to make a decrease in their Cash Conversion Cycle in order to reduce the cash gap. Because of the significant statistical outcomes, we reject our null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H₁). Therefore managers can generate high profits for their firms by managing the Cash Conversion Cycle CCC efficiently and keeping each different component (accounts receivables, accounts payables, inventory) to a balanced level.

Implications

Working Capital Management is a vital base of profitable businesses. It is the duty of every manager to keep it running and to utilize the cash flows to earn the profits for the firms. All the firms need a sufficient amount of Working Capital for maintaining survival of the business. Hence it has implications in every field of life.

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